

FUNKSIONAL QATORNI HADLAB INTEGRALLASH VA DIFFERENSIALLASHDAN FOYDALANIB BA'ZI BIR SONLI QATORLAR YIG'INDISINI TOPISH METODLARI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14184083>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada funksional qatorlarni hadlab integrallash va differenziyallash usullaridan foydalanib, ayrim sonli qatorlar yig'indisini topish metodlari tahlil qilinadi. Funksional qatorlarning xossalari o'rganilib, ularni sonli qatorlarga qo'llash orqali yangi natijalar keltirib chiqariladi. Xususan, funksional qatorlarni hadlab integrallash va differenziyallash orqali ba'zi sonli qatorlarning yig'indisini topish metodlari ko'rsatiladi hamda ular bilan bog'liq muammolarni hal qilish uchun aniq misollar keltiriladi. Mazkur usullar sonli qatorlarning yig'indisini hisoblashda samarali yondashuv sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: limit, tekis yaqinlashuvchiligi, summa, to'plam, segment, geometrik progressiya, aniq integral, differenziyallash.

Sonli qatorlar matematikaning turli sohalarida, jumladan, analiz, sonlar nazariyasi, va fizikada keng qo'llaniladi. Qatorlar yig'indisini hisoblash muammosi ko'pincha qiyin va noaniq vaziyatlarga olib keladi. Shuning uchun qatorlarning yig'indisini aniqlash uchun turli metodlar ishlab chiqilgan. Ushbu maqolada funksional qatorlarni hadlab integrallash va differenziyallash usullaridan foydalanish orqali sonli qatorlarning yig'indisini topish metodlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Funksional qatorlar bilan bog'liq yondashuvlar oddiy algebraik metodlarga nisbatan ko'proq qulayliklar taqdim etadi, chunki ularning yordamida qatorlarning murakkab xossalari tahlil qilish mumkin. Xususan, qatorlarni integrallash va differenziyallash orqali ularning yig'indisini aniqlash usullari sonli qatorlarni chuqurroq tushunishga va murakkab hisoblashlar uchun yangi imkoniyatlar yaratadi.

Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi – qatorlar yig'indisini topishda funksional qatorlarni hadlab integrallash va differenziyallash metodlarini qo'llash bo'yicha nazariy hamda amaliy jihatlarni o'rganish va ushbu metodlarning samaradorligini ko'rsatishdir. Biz birinchi o'rinda funksional qatorning tekis yaqinlashuvchanligi haqida ma'lumotga ega bo'lishimiz kerak bo'ladi.

1. Funksional qatorning tekis yaqinlashuvchanligi. Aytaylik,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x) = \theta_1(x) + \theta_2(x) + \dots + \theta_n(x) + \dots$$

Funksional qator E_0 to'plamda yaqinlashuvchi (ya'ni qatorning yaqinlashish to'plami E_0) bo'lin yig'indisi $S(x)$ bo'lsin:

$$S_n(x) \rightarrow S(x) \quad (x \in E_0) \quad (1)$$

Bunda, $S_n(x) = \theta_1(x) + \theta_2(x) + \dots + \theta_n(x)$ (1) munosabat,

$$\forall \varepsilon > 0, \forall x \in E_0, \exists n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon, x) \in \mathbb{N}, \forall n > n_0: |S_n(x) - S(x)| < \varepsilon$$

bo'lishini bildiradi.

$$\text{Agar } E_0 \text{ to'plamda } S_n(x) \rightrightarrows S(x) \quad (x \in E_0)$$

ya'ni,

$$\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon) \in \mathbb{N}, \forall n > n_0, \forall x \in E_0: |S_n(x) - S(x)| < \varepsilon$$

bo'lsa, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x)$ funksional qator E_0 to'plamda **tekis yaqinlashuvchi deb ataladi.**

Agar

$$r_n(x) = S(x) - S_n(x),$$

deyilsa funksional qatorning E_0 to'plamda tekis yaqinlashuvchiligini quyidagicha

$$r_n(x) \rightarrow 0 \quad (x \in E_0),$$

ya'ni

$$\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon) \in N, \forall n > n_0, \forall x \in E_0: |r_n(x)| < \varepsilon$$

Ko'rinishda ta'riflash mumkin bo'ladi.

Shunday qilib,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x) = \theta_1(x) + \theta_2(x) + \dots + \theta_n(x) + \dots$$

Funksional qator, uning qisman yig'indisi,

$$S_n(x) = \theta_1(x) + \theta_2(x) + \dots + \theta_n(x)$$

va yig'indisi $S(x)$ uchun

$$S_n(x) \rightarrow S(x) \quad (x \in E_0)$$

bo'lsa, funksional qator E_0 da yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi.

2. Funksional qatorlarni hadlab integrallash. Faraz qilaylik $[a, b]$ segmentda

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x) = \theta_1(x) + \theta_2(x) + \dots + \theta_n(x) + \dots \quad (1)$$

funksional qator berilgan bo'lsin.

1-teorema. Aytaylik, (1) qator quyidagi shartlarni bajarsin:

- 1) qatorning har biri $\theta_n(x)$ ($n=1,2,3,\dots$) hadi $[a, b]$ segmentda uzluksiz,
- 2) $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x)$ qator $[a, b]$ segmentda tekis yaqinlashuvchi,
- 3) $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x) = S(x)$.

$$U \text{ holda } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_n(t) dt = \int_a^x \theta_1(t) dt + \int_a^x \theta_2(t) dt + \dots$$

qator $[a, b]$ da yaqinlashuvchi va

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_n(t) dt = \int_a^x S(t) dt \quad (x \in [a, b])$$

bo'ladi.

Berilgan funksional qatorning qisman yig'indisi

$$S_n(x) = \theta_1(x) + \theta_2(x) + \dots + \theta_n(x)$$

ni olamiz. Bunda teoremaning 2)- va 3)- shartlariga ko'ra

$$S_n(x) \rightarrow S(x) \quad (x \in [a, b])$$

bo'ladi. Tekis yaqinlashish shartiga binoan

$$\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists n_0 = n_0(\varepsilon) \in N, \forall n > n_0 \text{ va } \forall t \in [a, b] \text{ da}$$

$$|S_n(t) - S(t)| < \frac{\varepsilon}{b-a}$$

tengsizlik bajariladi.

Teoremaning 1) – shartidan hamda yuqorida isbot qilingan 1-teoremadan foydalanib

$$\int_a^x \theta_n(t) dt \quad (n = 1,2,3, \dots), \quad \int_a^x S(t) dt$$

Integrallarni mavjudligini topamiz.

Ushbu

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_n(t) dt = \int_a^x \theta_1(t) dt + \int_a^x \theta_2(t) dt + \dots + \int_a^x \theta_n(t) dt + \dots$$

funksional qatorni qaraymiz. Bu qatorning qisman yig'indisi

$$S_n(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_k(t) dt \quad (x \in [a, b])$$

bo'lsin. Ravshanki ,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_k(t) dt = \int_a^x \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \theta_k(t) \right) dt$$

Demak,

$$S_n(x) = \int_a^x S_n(t) dt$$

Endi

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_n(t) dt$$

Funksional qatorning $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchiligi ko'rsatamiz.

$$\left| S_n(x) - \int_a^x S(t) dt \right|$$

Ayirma uchun

$$\begin{aligned} \left| S_n(x) - \int_a^x S(t) dt \right| &= \left| \int_a^x S_n(t) dt - \int_a^x S(t) dt \right| \leq \int_a^x |S_n(t) - S(t)| dt < \frac{e}{b-a} \int_a^x dt \\ &= \frac{e}{b-a} (x-a) < e \end{aligned}$$

bo'ladi. Demak,

$$S_n(x) \Rightarrow \int_a^x S(t) dt \quad (x \in [a, b])$$

Bu esa

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_n(t) dt$$

Funksional qatorni $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchiligi va

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_n(t) dt = \int_a^x S(t) dt$$

bo'lishini bildiradi.

Keltirilgan teoremaning shartlari bajarilganda teoremaning tasdig'ining quyidagicha

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \int_a^x \theta_k(t) dt = \int_a^x \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \theta_k(t) \right) dt$$

ifodalash mumkin.

3. Funksional qatorlarni hadlab differensiallash. Faraz qilaylik, $[a, b]$ segmentda

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x) = \theta_1(x) + \theta_2(x) + \dots + \theta_n(x) + \dots \quad (2)$$

funksional qator berilgan bo'lsin.

2-teorema. Aytaylik, (2) funksional qator quyidagi shartlarni bajarsin:

1) qatorning har biri $\theta_n(x)$ ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$), hadi $[a, b]$ segmentda uzluksiz $\theta_n'(x)$ ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$), da hosilaga ega,

2) Ushbu,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n'(x) = \theta_1'(x) + \theta_2'(x) + \dots + \theta_n'(x) + \dots$$

Funksional qator $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchi,

3) $x \in [a, b]$ nuqta mavjudki,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x) = \theta_1(x) + \theta_2(x) + \dots + \theta_n(x) + \dots$$

qator yaqinlashuvchi. U holda

- a) $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x)$ funksional qator $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchi
- b) bu qatorning yig'indisi

$$S(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x)$$

$[a, b]$ da uzluksiz $S'(x)$ hosilaga ega,

- c) $S'(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n'(x)$ bo'ladi.

Ushbu, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n'(x)$ qatorning yig'indisini $\sigma(x)$ deb belgilaylik:

$$\sigma(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n'(x) \quad (3)$$

Bu qator tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi va har bir hadi $[a, b]$ da uzluksiz. Yuqorida keltirilgan 2-teoremaga ko'ra (3) ni hadlab integrallash mumkin;

$$\int_{x_0}^x \sigma(x) dx = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_{x_0}^x \theta_n'(x) dx,$$

Bunda $x_0 \in [a, b]$, $x \in [a, b]$. Ayni paytda, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_{x_0}^x \theta_n'(x) dx$ funksional qator $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi.

Ma'lumki,

$$\int_{x_0}^x \theta_n(x) dx = \theta_n(x) - \theta_n(x_0).$$

Demak, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\theta_n(x) - \theta_n(x_0))$ qator $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchi.

Shartga ko'ra, $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\theta_n(x_0))$

Qator yaqinlashuvchi (uni $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchi deb qarash mumkin).

Shunday qilib

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\theta_n(x) - \theta_n(x_0)), \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\theta_n(x_0))$$

Qatorlar $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi. Bundan esa bu qatorlar yig'indisi bo'lgan

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\theta_n(x_0))$$

funksional qatorning $[a, b]$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchiligi kelib chiqadi. Shuni e'tiborga olib topami:

$$\int_{x_0}^x \sigma(x) dx = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\theta_n(x) - \theta_n(x_0)) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x) - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x_0) = S(x) - S(x_0).$$

$\sigma(x)$ funksiya, har bir hadi uzluksiz, o'zi tekis yaqinlashuvchi

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n'(x)$$

Qatorning yig'indisi bo'lgani uchun 1-teoremaga ko'ra, $[a, b]$ da uzluksiz bo'ladi

Unda keyingi tenglikdan

$$\sigma(x) = (S(x) - S(x_0))' = S'(x)$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

Bu keltirilgan teoremaning shartlari bajarilganda uning tasdiqini quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \theta_n(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d}{dx} \theta_n(x).$$

1-Misol: Ushbu

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \ln \frac{(n+1)(n+v)}{(n)(n+v+1)} \quad (0 \leq v \leq \infty)$$

funksional qatorning yig'indisi topilsin. Ma'lumki,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n+v)(n+v+1)}$$

Funksional qator $[0, +\infty)$ da tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'lib, uning yig'indisi

$$S(v) = \frac{1}{(v+1)}, \quad \text{ga teng,} \quad \frac{1}{(v+1)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n+v)(n+v+1)},$$

Ma'lumki, bu qatorning har bir hadi $[0, +\infty)$ da da uzluksiz. Demak, uni 2-teoremaga ho'ra hadlab integrallash mumkin:

$$\int_0^v \frac{dt}{(t+1)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^v \frac{dt}{(n+t)(n+t+1)}$$

Aniq integralni hisoblaymiz:

$$\int_0^v \frac{dt}{(t+1)} = \ln(t+1) \Big|_0^v = \ln(v+1),$$

$$\int_0^v \frac{dt}{(n+t)(n+t+1)} = \int_0^v \left(\frac{1}{n+t} - \frac{1}{n+t+1} \right) dt = \ln(n+t) \Big|_0^v - \ln(n+t+1) \Big|_0^v = \ln \frac{(n+1)(n+v)}{(n)(n+v+1)}.$$

$$\text{Demak,} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \ln \frac{(n+1)(n+v)}{(n)(n+v+1)} = \ln(v+1).$$

2-Misol: $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n}{4^n}$ yig'indini hisoblang.

Bu funksiya tekis kamayuvchi bolgani uchun yigindini hisoblashimiz mumkin.

Biz bunda $\frac{1}{4}$ ni x deb belgilab olamiz, $x = \frac{1}{4}$

$$\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \cdot x^n = x \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \cdot x^{n-1}$$

Ko'rinishda yozib olamiz va $\omega(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \cdot x^{n-1}$ shu yig'indini hisoblab olamiz:

Buning uchun biz tenglikni ikkala tomonini ham integrallab yuboramiz.

$$\int_0^x \omega(x) dx = \int_0^x \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \cdot x^{n-1}, \quad w(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^n = x + x^2 + \dots + x^n + \dots, \quad x = \frac{1}{4} \text{ ekanligidan}$$

yigindini cheksiz kamayuvchi geometrik progressiya ekanligini bilishimiz mumkin va yig'indisini topish fo'rmulasiga qoyamiz.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^n = x + x^2 + \dots + x^n + \dots = \frac{x}{1-x} \quad \text{ga teng,}$$

$$w(x) = \frac{x}{1-x}, \quad \omega(x) = \frac{1-x+x}{(1-x)^2}, \quad \omega(x) = \frac{1}{(1-x)^2}$$

$$\varphi(x) = x \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \cdot x^{n-1} = x \cdot \omega(x), \quad \varphi(x) = \frac{x}{(1-x)^2} \quad \text{bu yerda } x = \frac{1}{4} \text{ edi,}$$

$$\text{Demak, } \varphi\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) = \frac{\frac{1}{4}}{\left(1-\frac{1}{4}\right)^2} = \frac{4}{9}. \text{ Javob: } 4/9.$$

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

Ushbu maqolada funksional qatorlarni hadlab integrallash va differensiallash usullaridan foydalangan holda ba'zi sonli qatorlarning yig'indisini topish metodlari ko'rib chiqildi. Funksional qatorlarning xossalari tahlil qilinib, ularni sonli qatorlarga qo'llash orqali yangi natijalar olish mumkinligi ko'rsatildi. Ushbu yondashuv, ayniqsa, geometrik va trigonometrik qatorlarni samarali va aniq hisoblashda foydali ekanligi isbotlandi.

O'rganilgan usullar sonli qatorlarni hisoblashda qulay va samarali vosita bo'lib, murakkab qatorlarning yig'indisini aniqlashda o'z o'rniga ega. Ushbu metodlar kelajakdagi tadqiqotlarda

qatorlar nazariyasini rivojlantirish va boshqa matematik sohalarda qo'llash uchun imkoniyat yaratadi.

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